

FIRE AND POST FIRE PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY AND POLYCARBONATE COMPOSITE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Yousof M. Ghazzawi^{1,2,3}, Asanka P. Basnayake^{1,2}, Andres F. Osorio⁴, Juan Hidalgo Medina⁴, Michael T. Heitzmann^{1,2}

¹School of Mechanical and Mining Engineering, the University of Queensland, Australia

²Centre for Advanced Materials Processing and Manufacturing (AMPAM), the University of Queensland, Australia

³SABIC plastic application development centre, SABIC, Saudi Arabia

⁴School of Civil Engineering, the University of Queensland, Australia

Keywords: Fire performance; Thermoplastic thermoset; Polycarbonate; Epoxy; Post-fire properties

ABSTRACT

Fire performance of continuous glass fibre reinforced polycarbonate thermoplastic composite is evaluated against the fire performance of continuous glass fibre reinforced epoxy thermoset composite. Both composites had a fibre volume fraction of 47% and nominal thickness of 3.9 mm. Plain weave fabric was used with both composite. PC composite was manufactured using film stacking; while epoxy composite was manufactured using light resin transfer moulding. The fire performance of the two composites were compared at incident heat fluxes of 25 kW/m², 35 kW/m², and 50 kW/m². Post-fire four bending test was used to investigate the post fire residual mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are considered in a wide range of applications such as aerospace, construction, railway, and automotive. Due to well-known properties and process conditions, thermoset composite are still dominating the composite market with over 90% of continuous fibre composites market share. However, thermoplastic composites are increasingly replacing thermosets in applications where low cost, high impact strength, and recyclability are desired.

This is due to the fact that thermosets are more mature and have been used by industry for some time. The fire performance of thermoplastic composites has also been investigated. Nonetheless, due to its current low market share and a large diversity in matrix choice thermoplastic, the research for this group of composites is less comprehensive. A large proportion of the work is focused around chopped fibre composites [15-22].

There are only a few articles comparing the fire performance of thermosets to thermoplastics and it is mostly done on high performance composites [23].

This study aims to compare the fire performance of an engineering thermoplastic, polycarbonate (PC), to the fire performance of a thermoset with similar classification, Bisphenol A based epoxy resin. For a reasonable comparison, both composites have the same fibre volume fraction, similar densities, comparable thicknesses, and are tested under the same conditions.

Cone calorimetry was used to investigate the fire performance of glass fibre reinforced PC and epoxy. The two composite are compared in terms of heat release rate, burning time, time to ignition, critical heat flux, mass loss rate, and char yield.

Four-point bending tests were performed to compare the post fire mechanical properties of epoxy and PC composites in terms of bending strength and flexural modulus.

2 MATERIAL

SABIC PC 2200 polycarbonate copolymer with melt index of 22 g per 10 min, density of 1200 kg/m³, and glass transition temperature of 147°C was used to make the thermoplastic composite in the study. Ampreg22 epoxy was used with fast hardener. The glass transition temperature of the mix is 115°C and the density is 1147 kg/m³.

The glass fibre reinforced Polycarbonate composites were manufactured using film stacking. The films were dried for 4h at 100°C. After drying, the fabrics were laid up with the films interleaved and compression moulded at 270°C under a constant pressure of 2 MPa for 10 min. Samples were cooled to 50°C while maintaining pressure prior to releasing the press. The glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites were manufactured using light resin transfer moulding. The resin was cured at room temperature for 24 hours under vacuum then post cured at 50°C for 16 hours. 17 layers of plain weave fabric with areal weight of 280 g/m² were used to make a 250 x 250 mm plates of PC and epoxy composites. All plates had a nominal thickness of 6 mm and were cut to 100 x 100 mm samples for the cone calorimeter test using waterjet cutting.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

Cone calorimetry (Fire testing technology, Icone calorimeter) test was conducted according to ISO 5660-1 to compare the fire performance of the two composites in terms of Heat Release Rate (HRR), Time to ignition (Ti), mass loss, and Critical Heat Flux (CHF). The test was carried out at heat flux values of 25 kW/m², 35 kW/m², and 50 kW/m². Sample size was 100 x 100 mm. The edge and rear face was wrapped with an aluminium foil in order to minimise radiation heat losses and prevent spurious mass loss readings due to melting and dripping. The back face of the sample was insulated using ceramic wool to minimise heat losses. A retaining frame as suggested in ISO 5660-1 was used to restrain the exposed surface of the sample and prevent contact with the heating element.

Four point bending test were performed in accordance with ASTM D6272 to investigate the pre and post-fire mechanical properties of the composite samples before and after exposure to fire. Sample size was 100 x 10 mm. Samples were taken from different areas of the burned 100 x 100 mm samples.

4 RESULTS

This section summaries the results of the Cone calorimeter and flexural bending tests performed on the two composite types.

4.1 Fire testing

Fire testing was carried out for three specimens for each composite at the three different incident heat fluxes to compare Glass Fiber Reinforced Epoxy composite (GFREC) to Glass Fiber Reinforced PC Composite (GFRPC) in terms of time to ignition (Ti), Peak Heat Release Rate (pHRR), Mean Heat Release Rate (mHRR), Total Heat Release (tHR), Char Yield (CY), Critical Heat Flux (CHF) and mass loss. Results are reported with 90% confidence interval as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Fire testing results for PC and epoxy composites

		HF (kW/m ²)	GFRPC	GFREC
Ti	(S)	25	618.67 ± 55.57	183.00 ± 5.84
		35	248.00 ± 2.92	107.00 ± 4.46
		50	116.00 ± 0.00	59.00 ± 2.92
pHRR	(kW/m ²)	25	122.92 ± 10.54	381.29 ± 58.90
		35	165.28 ± 29.48	423.00 ± 47.70
		50	195.51 ± 21.46	467.78 ± 17.06
mHRR	(kW/m ²)	25	85.52 ± 8.75	222.55 ± 15.43
		35	117.09 ± 18.49	226.18 ± 25.19
		50	123.25 ± 7.50	257.18 ± 1.16
tHR	(MJ/m ²)	25	30.79 ± 3.15	67.88 ± 4.71
		35	39.81 ± 6.29	65.59 ± 7.30
		50	38.21 ± 2.32	65.58 ± 0.30
CY	(%)	25	34.99 ± 5.63	7.81 ± 1.53
		35	24.76 ± 4.36	8.00 ± 2.23
		50	19.32 ± 0.78	7.18 ± 1.59
CHF	(kW/m ²)		23	11

In terms of time to ignition, Polycarbonate composite takes at least twice as much time to ignite in comparison to epoxy. For instance, at 25 kW/m² incident heat flux, polycarbonate takes around 618 s to ignite; while epoxy takes only 183 s.

As heat release rate is concerned, Polycarbonate composites exhibit less than half peak heat release rate compared to the epoxy composite. For example, at an incident heat flux of 35 kW/m², polycarbonate composite has an average peak heat release rate of 165.28 kW/m²; while epoxy composite has a peak heat release rate of 467.78 kW/m² at the same incident heat flux. Figure 1 shows the heat release rate for PC and epoxy glass fibre composite

Figure 1: Heat release rate for PC and epoxy composites at an incident heat flux of A) 25 kW/m², B) 35 kW/m², C) 50 kW/m²

The char yield of polycarbonate is much higher than epoxy. While polycarbonate has a char yield ranging from 35% at 25 kW/m² heat flux to 19% at 50kW/m² heat flux, epoxy has a very low char yield of about 8 %.

In terms of critical heat flux, PC composites ignite at an incident heat flux of 23 kW/m². While epoxy composite samples ignite at 11 kW/m² incident heat flux.

In terms of mass loss, epoxy composite samples start losing mass very rapidly, right from the onset of ignition, while for PC composite samples the onset of the mass loss is only pronounced after 50 to 100 s from the time to ignition depending on incident heat flux

Figure 2: mass loss for PC and epoxy composites at an incident heat flux of A) 25 kW/m², B) 35 kW/m², C) 50 kW/m²

4.2 Flexural test

Figure 3 demonstrates the flexural test results for glass fiber reinforced PC prior to and post fire exposure were samples were tested from different part of the burned samples from icone test. Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite sample did not have any strength left after exposure to fire; while glass fiber reinforced PC samples have post fire mechanical properties of 7% when tested at 25kW/m². When tested at higher incident heat fluxes, post fire mechanical properties of PC composite are found to be less than 5% at 35kW/m² and almost 0% at 50kW/m². As shown in Figure 3 the remaining performance of the composite is heavily influenced by the sampling location of the post-fire flexural test samples. At 25kW/m² heat flux, the strength reduces by more than 70% from the edge of the specimen to the center.

Figure 3: Prior to and post fire flexural properties of glass fibre reinforced epoxy/PC

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Fire performance of glass fibre reinforced epoxy/PC composite

As shown in Table 1, PC composite is superior to epoxy composite in terms of fire performance. PC composite has lower mean heat release rate, peak heat release rate, and mass loss rate. In addition, PC composites takes at least twice as much time to ignite when compared to epoxy composites at a similar incident heat flux. Critical heat flux of polycarbonate is 23 kW/m²; while it is 11 kW/m² for epoxy. This means that epoxy composite will ignite at approximately 220°C; while PC ignites when exposed to temperature around 400°C or higher. The significant difference in fire performance between the two resins is remarkable considering they have a similar chemical structure; suggesting that knowing the chemical structure of a polymer is not enough to estimate its fire performance.

5.2 Post fire mechanical properties

As indicated in Figure 3, PC composite has a post fire flexural strength of around 7% when tested at an incident heat flux of 25%. This is believed to be a result of PC having a char yield of 35% at this heat flux. It is worth noting that the heat char yield is greatly affected by the heat flux and reduces from 35% at 25 kW/m² heat flux to 19% at 50 kW/m². Epoxy composite had no post fire mechanical properties left after testing. This is a result of the much lower char yield of the epoxy resin, which was only measured at around 7% which is very low when compared to PC. Figure 4 is an SEM image for PC composite after fire testing. The image shows that some char is still attached to the fabric; indicating a residual strength remaining for PC composites.

Figure 4: SEM images for PC Reinforced samples after cone calorimeter testing.

6 CONCLUSION

fibre reinforced PC (thermoplastic composite) was found to be superior to glass fibre reinforced epoxy (thermoset composite) in terms of fire performance in this study. Despite having a comparable fibre volume fraction, PC composites have a better time to ignition, heat release rate, and critical heat flux than epoxy composite samples. The difference between epoxy and PC composites is remarkable considering the similarities in the chemical backbone of the two resins as they both made of BisphenolA monomer.

Unsurprisingly, char yield has an effect on post fire mechanical properties. For the lowest heat flux tested PC retained 7% of the flexural strength. It is worth noting that the post fire performance is greatly affected by the sample location and the heat flux. For more realistic fire scenarios, this highlights an interesting: The residual structural performance is not just a simple function of char yield, but is a rather complex function of the thermal history of the sample during the fire event.

In this study, the analysis was performed on a certain epoxy matrix (Bisphenol A resin and Polyoxyalkyleneamine/cyclohexylamine hardner). However, many different epoxy resin chemistries exist and consequently their performance could differ greatly to the system compared here.

References

1. Feih, S., et al., *Influence of water content on failure of phenolic composites in fire*. Polymer Degradation and Stability, 2008. 93(2): p. 376-382.
2. Grigoriou, K. and A.P. Mouritz, *Comparative assessment of the fire structural performance of carbon-epoxy composite and aluminium alloy used in aerospace structures*. Materials & Design, 2016. 108: p. 699-706.
3. Kandare, E., P. Luangtriratana, and B.K. Kandola, *Fire reaction properties of flax/epoxy laminates and their balsa-core sandwich composites with or without fire protection*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2014. 56: p. 602-610.
4. Kandare, E., et al., *Thermo-mechanical Responses of Fiber-reinforced Epoxy Composites Exposed to High Temperature Environments. Part I: Experimental Data Acquisition*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2010. 44(26): p. 3093-3114.
5. Kim, M., J. Choe, and D.G. Lee, *Development of the fire retardant glass fabric/carbonized phenolic composite*. Composite Structures, 2016. 148: p. 191-197.
6. Quang Dao, D., et al., *Determination of characteristic parameters for the thermal decomposition of epoxy resin/carbon fibre composites in cone calorimeter*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, 2013. 38(19): p. 8167-8178.
7. Alonso, M.V., M.L. Auad, and S. Nutt, *Short-fiber-reinforced epoxy foams*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2006. 37(11): p. 1952-1960.
8. Eesaee, M. and A. Shojaei, *Effect of nanoclays on the mechanical properties and durability of novolac phenolic resin/woven glass fiber composite at various chemical environments*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2014. 63: p. 149-158.
9. Fiorina, M., et al., *Spring-in prediction for carbon/epoxy aerospace composite structure*. Composite Structures, 2017. 168: p. 739-745.
10. Kim, M., J. Choe, and D.G. Lee, *Development of the fire-retardant sandwich structure using an aramid/glass hybrid composite and a phenolic foam-filled honeycomb*. Composite Structures, 2016. 158: p. 227-234.
11. Kandola, B.K., et al., *Empirical and numerical approach for optimisation of fire and mechanical performance in fire-retardant glass-reinforced epoxy composites*. Fire Safety Journal, 2008. 43(1): p. 11-23.
12. Kandola, B.K., L. Krishnan, and J.R. Ebdon, *Blends of unsaturated polyester and phenolic resins for application as fire-resistant matrices in fibre-reinforced composites: Effects of added flame retardants*. Polymer Degradation and Stability, 2014. 106: p. 129-137.

13. Kurkin, E.I. and V.O. Sadykova, *Application of Short Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials Multilevel Model for Design of Ultra-light Aerospace Structures*. Procedia Engineering, 2017. 185: p. 182-189.
14. Dong, M., X. Gu, and S. Zhang, *Effects of compound oxides on the fire performance of polypropylene composite*. Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, 2014. 53(19): p. 8062-8068.
15. Dong, M., et al., *Effects of acidic sites in HA zeolite on the fire performance of polystyrene composite*. Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, 2013. 52(26): p. 9145-9154.
16. Tang, W., et al., *Effects of surface acid-activated kaolinite on the fire performance of polypropylene composite*. Thermochemica Acta, 2017. 648: p. 1-12.
17. Yang, W., et al., *Fire and mechanical performance of nanoclay reinforced glass-fiber/PBT composites containing aluminum hypophosphite particles*. Composites Part A, 2011. 42(7): p. 794-800.
18. Yang, W., et al., *Effect of rare earth hypophosphite and melamine cyanurate on fire performance of glass-fiber reinforced poly(1,4-butylene terephthalate) composites*. Thermochemica Acta, 2011. 526(1): p. 185-191.
19. Jiao, C., et al., *Fire hazard reduction of hollow glass microspheres in thermoplastic polyurethane composites*. Journal of Hazardous Materials, 2017. 332: p. 176-184.
20. Kandola, B.K. and R. Toqueer-ul-haq, *The effect of fibre content on the thermal and fire performance of polypropylene– glass composites*. Fire and Materials, 2012. 36(8): p. 603-613.
21. Xue, M., et al., *A commercial phosphorous–nitrogen containing intumescent flame retardant for thermoplastic polyurethane*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2014. 131(2): p. n/a-n/a.
22. Zhang, Y., et al., *A novel surface modification of carbon fiber for high-performance thermoplastic polyurethane composites*. Applied Surface Science, 2016. 382: p. 144-154.
23. Benoit, V., L. Cédric, and C. Alexis, *Post fire behavior of carbon fibers Polyphenylene Sulfide- and epoxy-based laminates for aeronautical applications: A comparative study*. Materials & Design, 2014. 63: p. 56-68.